

Heterocyclic Compounds. Part VI. Synthesis and Reactions of Some Pyrrolidine-2,3-diones and Pyrrolidine-2,3,5-triones

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Several pyrrolidine-2,3-diones have been synthesised by condensation of oxalacetic ester and phenylpyruvic acid with different aldehydes and amines. In some cases, cinchoninic acids are the products of condensation. A few pyrrolidine-2,3,5-triones have also been prepared by condensing diethyl oxalate with β -substituted acetamides in presence of sodium ethoxide. The properties and reactions of the pyrrolidine diones and triones have been studied.

The present communication is a continuation of our previous work¹ and describes the condensation of phenylpyruvic acid and oxalacetic ester with different aldehydes and amines to yield pyrrolidine-2,3-diones. In some cases, the condensation products are cinchoninic acid derivatives or the Schiff's bases formed by interaction of the aldehydes and amines.

The pyrrolidine diones, prepared from oxalacetic ester, are generally high-melting crystalline substances and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Dions.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
I	185°	50%	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄ NCl	64.3	63.8	4.9	4.5	..	..
II	183°	47	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ NCl	..	..	..	..	4.2	3.8
III	184°	38	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ NCl ₂	58.0	58.2	4.1	3.8	..	..
IV	204°	47	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	..	..	..	..	7.3	7.0
V	149°	10	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ NCl	..	..	..	..	3.5	3.6
VI	190°	19	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	..	..	..	..	8.8	8.6
VII	202°	33	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ NCl ₂	58.3	58.2	4.3	3.8	..	..
VIII	195°	12	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ NCl ₂	..	..	..	..	3.7	3.3
IX	205°	30	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂ Cl ₂	52.3	52.3	3.5	3.2	..	..

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|--|---|
| (I): R = C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i>); | R ₁ = Ph. |
| (II): " " ; | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .Me (<i>p</i>). |
| (III): " " ; | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .Cl (<i>p</i>). |
| (IV): " " ; | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (<i>p</i>). |
| (V): " " ; | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .OMe (<i>p</i>). |
| (VI): R = Ph; | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .N (<). |
| (VII): R = C ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂ (<i>o,p</i>); | R ₁ = Ph. |
| (VIII): " " | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .Cl (<i>p</i>). |
| " " | R ₁ = C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (<i>p</i>). |

In these condensations, equimolecular quantities of the three reactants were taken in ethanol and boiled on a water bath for 15 to 20 minutes; the mixture was kept at room temperature to yield crystalline pyrrolidine diones. It has been observed that the minimum period required for the different diones is not the same for all. In some cases, Schiff's bases were the products obtained immediately on adding the reactants, which went into solution on heating and yielded pyrrolidine diones on keeping, but in other cases pasty or oily masses were obtained. The structures of the Schiff's bases were confirmed by preparing them directly by the reaction of the corresponding aldehyde and amine and taking a mixed melting point with the condensation product. These reactions are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Benzaldehyde.	Aniline.	Product obtained.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1. <i>p</i> -Methoxy	2,5-DiMe	Oil		..	..	..
2 Itself	2,4-DiMe	Paste		..	..	..
3 <i>p</i> -Chloro	2-Aminopyridine	..		..	..	..
4 Do	<i>p</i> -Me	Schiff's base	123°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ NCl	5.9	6.1
5 Do	<i>p</i> -OMe		120°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ONCl	5.8	5.7
6 2,4-Dichloro	<i>p</i> -Chloro		123°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NCl ₂	5.0	4.9

From a study of these reaction products, experimental conditions, etc., the following observations can be made.

(1) Substituted anilines act slowly to form pyrrolidine diones, whereas aniline itself yields the corresponding diones easily.

(2) *p*-Toluidine and *p*-anisidine form Schiff's bases immediately after adding the reactants which on further warming and keeping or condensing again with oxalacetic ester form pyrrolidine diones.

(3). Heterocyclic amines, such as, 2-aminopyridine, do not seem to react easily to form pyrrolidine diones.

(4) A chloro-group does not favour easy formation of pyrrolidine diones. 2,4-Dichlorobenzaldehyde is less active than *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde. Formation of pyrrolidine dione from 2,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde and *p*-chloroaniline is difficult and a poor yield of the dione is obtained.

(5) Nitroanilines react slowly and yield pyrrolidine diones after a long period.

The pyrrolidine-2,3-diones are insoluble in water, but are soluble in hot chloroform, benzene, acetic acid, and acetone and sparingly soluble in ethanol and light petroleum. These are relatively stable at high temperature. The keto group is strongly enolisable and induces the compounds an acid character. The enolic nature of these compounds is shown by the ferric chloride coloration and formation of methyl ethers and acetyl and benzoyl derivatives. The ketonic nature is indicated by the formation of oximes, phenyl-

hydrazones, anils, and the quinoxaline derivatives, obtained by heating the diones with *o*-phenylenediamines. Relevant derivatives are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Pyrrolidine dione.	Derivative.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
I	Ac	158°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₃ NCl	3.9	3.80
VII	Ac	250°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ NCl ₂	3.5	3.20
I	Bz	182°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ NCl	3.4	3.03
II	"	198°	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ NCl	3.2	3.30
VII	"	101°	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₃ NCl ₂	2.7	2.90
I	Quinoxaline	278°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	9.4	9.90
II	"	270°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	9.2	9.40
VII	"	205°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	9.9	10.10
I	OMe	88°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ NCl	4.1	3.70
II	"	101°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄ NCl	3.5	3.70
I	Phenyldiazone	137°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	9.2	9.38
II	"	170°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.9	9.10
III	"	209°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	8.8	8.70
I	Oxime	(a) 225°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.6	6.80
		(b) 179°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.7	6.80
II	"	(a) 185°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.8	6.60
		(b) 145°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.6	6.60
VII	"	(a) 230° (d)	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₃	6.1	6.30
		(b) 236°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ Cl ₃	5.9	6.30
I	Anil	224°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	6.8	6.40
II	"	229°	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	6.3	6.20
VII	"	133°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	5.8	6.00

The ethoxycarbonyl group in the pyrrolidine diones could easily be converted into methoxycarbonyl group by boiling the former with methanol, saturated with dry HCl gas.

In agreement with the observations of Schiff and Bertini² that the condensation of oxalacetic ester with benzaldehyde and β -naphthylamine affords pyrrolidine diones, the ester and amine have been found to react with *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde to yield two products which from the analytical data and the colour reaction with ferric chloride correspond to the relative Schiff's base and the expected pyrrolidine diones. Replacement of β -naphthylamine for α -isomer in the above condensation yielded pasty products from which no pure substance could be isolated.

The condensation of phenylpyruvic acid with α - and β -naphthylamines with *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde afforded cinchoninic acids. Their structures were confirmed by their acidic nature and further by decarboxylation by heating them above their melting points to the corresponding benzoquinoline derivatives. From the analogy with the data obtained before, their structures have been assigned as 2-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-phenylbenzo-(h)-quinoline and 2-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-phenylbenzo-(f)-quinoline respectively.

Although a large amount of work has been done on pyrrolidine diones, very little data³ are, however, available regarding the synthesis and reactions of pyrroliding triones.

4-Phenylpyrrolidine-2,3,5-trione⁴ (I) was synthesised by condensing diethyl oxalate with phenylacetamide in presence of sodium ethoxide.

The condensation of phenylacetamide with diethyl oxalate afforded 1,4-diphenylpyrrolidine-2,3,5-trione (II) as a crystalline solid.

[R=H(I) or Ph (II)]

Attempts to prepare pyrrolidine trione derivatives by the condensation of acetoacetamide and chloroacetamide with diethyl oxalate failed to provide the desired products. With chloroacetamide, however, oxalic acid was isolated.

The pyrrolidine triones (I and II) are crystalline, high-melting solids. They exhibit a bluish green coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride. Attempts to prepare an acetyl derivative or a 2,4-DNP failed to produce a definite product. With *o*-phenylenediamine, crystalline quinoxaline derivatives could, however, be isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Method for the Preparation of Pyrrolidine-2,3-diones.—An equimolecular mixture of diethyl oxalacetate or phenylpyruvic acid and the amine and the aldehyde was dissolved in absolute ethanol. The solution was boiled on a water bath for 15-20 mins. On keeping overnight, the pyrrolidine dione usually separated as a yellow solid which was filtered, washed with ethanol, and crystallised from dilute ethanol (Table I).

Methyl ethers as well as the acetyl, benzoyl, and quinoxaline derivatives from the pyrrolidine diones were prepared as described earlier. Oximes and phenylhydrazones from the latter were obtained as usual. The ethoxycarbonyl group in pyrrolidine dione was converted into methoxycarbonyl group as described previously¹.

*Condensation of Phenylpyruvic Acid with p-Chlorobenzaldehyde and β-Naphthylamine*⁵: 4-Carboxy-2-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-5,6-benzo-(f)-quinoline.—A mixture of phenylpyruvic

3. Skinner and Perkins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5569; Sheehan and Corey, *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 380; Skinner and Miller, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 977.

4. Howard *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, **80**, 3924.

5. Borsche, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 4072.

acid (1.64 g.), *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (1.4 g.) and β -naphthylamine (1.4 g.) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (25 ml) and the mixture was boiled for an hour on a water bath. On cooling, an orange solid separated. It was crystallised from dioxane in fine needles, m.p. 282°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 3.9. $C_{26}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires C, 76.1; H, 3.9%). The compound did not exhibit any coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-5,6-benzo-(f)-quinoline was obtained on decarboxylating the above acid by heating 1.0 g. of the compound at 290-95° on a sand bath for 2 hours. On cooling, a black solid was obtained which was extracted with chloroform and the latter was removed at room temperature, when a brownish solid was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol in yellowish prisms, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 3.5. $C_{25}H_{16}NCl$ requires N, 3.8%).

Condensation of Phenylpyruvic Acid with p-Chlorobenzaldehyde and α -Naphthylamine: 4-Carboxy-2-(p-chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-7,8-benzo-(h)-quinoline.—Phenylpyruvic acid (1.64 g.), *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (1.4 g.), and α -naphthylamine (1.4 g.) were taken in ethanol (25 ml) and boiled on a water bath for 1 hour. On keeping overnight, a brown solid was obtained which was crystallised from dilute dioxane in fine prisms, m.p. 270°, yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 4.1; N, 3.6. $C_{26}H_{16}O_2NCl$ requires C, 76.1; H, 3.9; N, 3.5%). It gave a negative $FeCl_3$ reaction.

2-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-5,6-benzquinoline was prepared from the above 4-carboxyquinoline by heating the compound to its melting point on a sand bath for 2 hours. On cooling, the black mass obtained was extracted with chloroform, the solvent removed, and the residue was crystallised from ethanol in prisms, m.p. 184°. (Found: N, 3.9. $C_{25}H_{16}NCl$ requires N, 3.8%).

Condensation of Oxalacetic Ester with p-Chlorobenzaldehyde and β -Naphthylamine.—Formation of (a) p-Chlorobenzylidene- β -naphthylamine and (b) 4-Ethoxycarbonyl-1-(β -naphthyl)-5-(p-chlorophenyl)-2,3-pyrrolidine Dione.—A mixture of oxalacetic ester (1.9 g.), *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (1.4 g.), and β -naphthylamine (1.4 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was boiled on a water bath for 1 hour. On cooling, a crystalline solid separated immediately. It was crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 120°.

The compound did not show any ferric chloride coloration. From the analytical data it was found to be the Schiff's base. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 4.1. $C_{16}H_{12}NCl$ requires C, 76.8; H, 4.5%).

On concentrating the mother liquor, a yellow solid (0.25 g.) separated. It was crystallised from ethanol to yield fine prisms, m.p. 160°. It developed a red coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride. From the colour test and analytical results it was found to be the pyrrolidine dione. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 4.8. $C_{25}H_{18}O_4NCl$ requires C, 67.7; H, 4.4%).

4-Phenylpyrrolidine-2,3,5-trione was prepared in the same manner as described by Skinner and Miller³. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 215° (lit.³ m.p. 215-17°). The compound showed a bluish green coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

Condensation of Phenylacetanilide with Diethyl Oxalate in presence of Sodium Ethoxide.
The reaction was carried out in the same manner as that for the preparation of the

preceding trione. The yellow solid obtained was filtered and washed with water and xylene alternately. It was crystallised from ethanol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 191°, yield 8.0 g. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 72.4; H, 4.1%). The compound showed a green ferric chloride coloration.

Attempted Condensation of Chloroacetamide⁷ with Ethyl Oxalate.—The condensation was carried out as usual. On removal of xylene, a brownish oil was obtained which was extracted with ether. On distilling the ether, yellowish white crystals separated. Recrystallisation from ethanol provided fine colorless needles, m.p. 100°. The compound gave a negative ferric chloride reaction. It did not contain any halogen or nitrogen and was soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence. From the analytical results the compound was found to be oxalic acid, confirmed by mixed m.p. determination.

Attempted Condensation of Acetoacetamide⁷ with Ethyl Oxalate.—The condensation was carried out in the same way as before, but only an oil was obtained, which did not solidify after steam distillation or extraction with ether. It was not worked up further.

*Condensation of 4-Phenylpyrrolidine-2,3,5-triones with *c*-Phenylenediamine to form Quinoxaline Derivatives.*—An equimolecular mixture of pyrrolidine-2,3,5-trione and *o*-phenylenediamine was taken in acetic acid and was refluxed for 1½ hours with a short air-condenser. On cooling, a yellow solid separated. It was recrystallised from either dilute ethanol or dilute acetic acid in fine yellow needles.

The quinoxaline derivative from 4-phenylpyrrolidine-2,3,5-trione obtained melted at 260°. (Found: N, 15.8. $C_{16}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 16.0%).

From 1,4-diphenylpyrrolidine-2,3,5-trione a quinoxaline derivative melting at 218° was obtained. (Found: N, 12.1. $C_{22}H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 12.5%).

Attempted Acetylation on Trioxopyrrolidine.—4-Phenyl-2,3,5-trioxopyrrolidine (0.4g.) was taken in acetic anhydride (1 ml) and 2 or 3 drops of pyridine were added to it. The mixture was then refluxed for half an hour and then poured into cold water. A brownish oil separated which on keeping in a refrigerator solidified to a paste. The pasty mass was treated with ethanol and charcoaled when a crystalline compound mixed with a pasty mass was obtained. It could not be purified for purposes of analysis.

6. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1957, p. 582.

7. Jacobs and "Heidelburger, "Organic Syntheses" Coll. Vol. I, p. 153.

8. Ref. No, 6, p. 401.